

Étapes	Contenu / Instructions	Exemple pour "Manger"	Réponses des élèves	Commentaires/Améliorations
A : Verbe	Verbe choisi par le professeur ou proposé par les élèves.	Manger		
B : Vocabulaire associé	Mots de vocabulaire en lien avec le verbe (objets, actions, contextes, etc.).	pomme, déjeuner, dîner, gourmand, faim		
C : Phrase affirmative (Présent)	Création d'une phrase affirmative au présent de l'indicatif.	Je mange une pomme.		
D : Question – Type ouverte	Créer une question ouverte dont la réponse sera la phrase affirmative. (Utiliser un mot interrogatif, incitant à développer la réponse.)	Qu'est-ce que tu manges quand tu as faim ?		
E : Question – Type fermée	Créer une question fermée dont la réponse attendue est la phrase affirmative (réponse brève ou oui/non, ou confirmation de la phrase).	Manges-tu une pomme ?		
F : Phrase négative	Transformer la phrase affirmative en forme négative.	Je ne mange pas de pomme.		
G : Question négative	Transformer la question (ouverte ou fermée) en forme négative.	Ne manges-tu pas de pomme ?		
H : Phrase connectée	Ajouter à la phrase affirmative une deuxième phrase en utilisant un connecteur logique (ex : car, parce que, donc, mais, etc.) pour expliquer ou enrichir l'idée.	Je mange une pomme parce que j'ai faim.		
I : Changement de temps	Changer le temps de la phrase et adapter la question en conséquence (par exemple, passage au passé composé ou futur simple).	J'ai mangé une pomme.		
		Qu'as-tu mangé hier ?		

Instructions for Independent Work with AI

1. Matrix Setup:

- Open your working file (Excel, Google Sheets, or another suitable format) that contains the matrix with the following columns:
 - Verb
 - Associated Vocabulary
 - Affirmative Sentence (Present)
 - Open-Ended Question
 - Closed-Ended Question
 - Negative Sentence
 - Negative Question
 - Connected Sentence
 - Tense Change
 - Student Responses
 - Comments/Improvements

2. Individual Completion:

- Fill in each column of the matrix following the exercise guidelines.
- Take time to carefully think through each step (e.g., constructing sentences, formulating questions, using logical connectors, etc.).

3. Using AI for Corrections and Suggestions:

- Once you have completed your work, copy the sentence or question you wish to have corrected.
- Open your AI interface (for example, via a chat or dedicated application) and ask for corrections or suggestions.
- Example requests:
 - *"Could you correct and improve this sentence? I eat an apple."*

- *"Here is my question: 'What do you eat when you are hungry?'. How can I improve it?"*
- The AI will provide you with detailed feedback and improvement suggestions for each element.

4. Integrating the Feedback:

- Copy the corrections and suggestions provided by the AI into the "Comments/Improvements" column.
- Revise your work accordingly by incorporating the given advice in the respective sections.

5. Self-Evaluation and Follow-Up:

- Review your entire matrix once the corrections have been integrated.
- If some points remain unclear or if you need additional examples, feel free to ask the AI further questions to deepen or clarify your doubts.

Teacher's Instructions

Exercise Preparation:

- Select or ask students to choose a verb (e.g., *manger*).
- Distribute the matrix (an adapted Excel file or Google Sheet) containing the following columns:
 - Verb
 - Associated Vocabulary
 - Affirmative Sentence (Present)
 - Open-Ended Question
 - Closed-Ended Question
 - Negative Sentence
 - Negative Question
 - Connected Sentence
 - Tense Change
 - Student Responses
 - Comments/Improvements

Activity Flow:

- **Steps 1-3:**
Students write down the verb, suggest associated vocabulary, and construct an affirmative sentence.
- **Step 4:**
They create an open-ended question and a closed-ended question whose answer is the affirmative sentence.
(Oral bonus: have them practice speaking by asking these questions to their classmates.)
- **Step 5:**
Transform the sentence and the questions into the negative form.

- **Step 6:**
Enrich the sentence with a logical connector to form a second sentence.
- **Step 7:**
Change the tense (e.g., switch to the passé composé) for both the sentence and the question.

Collaboration and Feedback:

- Organize group work (3 to 4 students) with assigned roles (e.g., writing, formulating questions, proofreading).
- Plan a collaborative exchange using Tencent Docs:
 - Each group shares its matrix on Tencent Docs for real-time review.
 - Both students and you provide comments and suggestions directly in the document.

Monitoring and Evaluation:

- Use the "Student Responses" column to track their work.
- Record areas for improvement and personalized feedback in the "Comments/Improvements" column.
- Conduct a collective synthesis at the end of the session to highlight strengths and possible improvements.